

The Analysis of Code-Switching found in the Twitter Account @natanattda

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Abstract : The phenomenon of code-switching occurs in everyday life as speech or text on social media. One example is found in Twitter, a social media platform that has received a lot of attention in recent years. This study aimed to determine (1) what types of code-switching are used and (2) why code-switching is used on Twitter accounts @natanattda. The research was carried out using qualitative methods. Reading and searching for tweets from the @natanattda account is a method of collecting data in this study. The theory applied when conducting this study was proposed by Poplack in Romaine (1995) to analyze the different types of code-switching. Another theory was proposed by Hoffman (1991) about the reasons for using code-switching. In this study, two points were discovered through data analysis. The first point was about the various types of code-switching, including Tag switching, Inter-sentential switching, and Intra-sentential switching. The second point was about the reasons for using code-switching. The most dominant type of code-switching found in the data is Inter-sentential switching. From the seven reasons for using the code-switching theory proposed by Hoffman (1991), only two reasons found from this account's tweets include talking about a particular topic and being emphatic about something (expressing solidarity). The most dominant reason for using code-switching found in the data is talking about a particular topic.

Keywords : *code-switching, types and reasons, Twitter*

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1. Introduction

Sociolinguistics is the study of the relationship between language and society. Sociolinguists are interested in why we speak differently in different social contexts as humans. They will be able to recognize language's social functions and how language is used to convey social meaning. The phenomenon of code-switching is also one of the things studied in Sociolinguistics. People occasionally change their code in social domains or situations. When there is a detectable change in the situation, such as introducing a new person, a speaker may switch to another language to demonstrate group membership and ethnicity with the recipient. Switches motivated by participants' identities and relationships frequently reveal movement along the solidarity/social distance dimension. Switching can also indicate changes in other dimensions, such as people's status relationships or the formality they interact with.

People choose different codes in different situations in everyday interactions. They may prefer specific codes or variations because they find it easier to discuss specific topics wherever they speak. People must use a specific code to express their emotions when communicating with one another. Most speakers occupy multiple codes and must use their chosen code whenever they speak to another person. The phenomenon of people having more than one code is called bilingualism or multilingualism (Wardhaugh, 1986, p.101). Spolsky (1998, p.45) defines a bilingual as "some functional abilities in a second language" in order to clarify the term bilingualism or multilingualism. This can range from having limited ability in one or more domains to commanding both languages fluently.

In linguistics, code-switching refers to switching between one or more languages, dialects, or language registers during conversations between people who speak more than one language. This language switch may only last a few sentences or even a single phrase. Code-switching, as defined by Gal and Wardhaugh, is a conversational strategy used to establish, cross, or destroy group boundaries, as well as to create, awaken, or change interpersonal relationships with rights and obligations (Wardhaugh, 1998, p.100). Code-switching occurs when speakers move from one language or language variation to another, usually in a conversation, email, or letter. For example, speakers switch from Indonesian to English or vice versa. Code-switching describes the process of moving people between registers, dialects, and languages during a conversation.

The majority of Indonesians are fluent in two languages. This is due to the fact that Indonesia has so many ethnic groups, each with its own regional language. Meanwhile, some Indonesians, particularly in metropolitan areas, already use English as their primary language. As a result, it is common to hear a switch between those two languages in the classroom or workplace. The phenomenon of code-switching frequently occurs in our daily lives, whether when speaking or sending messages over the internet. Furthermore, with the widespread use of social media today, many phenomena of language change can be found.

Several reviews of the related studies served as references in conducting this study. The first was from an article entitled *Code Switching in the Instructions of English Language Education* by Thomas and Retno (2016). This study focused on the different types and reasons for using code-switching ELESP lectures in their instructional languages. The second was an article entitled *Types of Code Switching Used in The Naked Traveler Novel* written by Dwinesa Anggraeni (2021). This study focused on identifying the types of code-switching found in Trinity's *The Naked Traveler Novel* and determining the most dominant type of code-switching found in Trinity's *The Naked Traveler Novel*. The last was an article entitled *English Code-Switching in Indonesian Magazine Articles* written by Indah Dwi Cahayany (2019). This study

focused on examining English code-switching in Indonesian language magazine articles. Compared to previous studies, there are several things that are different, namely in the data used. Aside from that, only some studies analyze the types and reasons for code-switching on Twitter. This study will focus on the types and reasons for code-switching in @natanattda's tweets from 2021 to 2022.

According to We Are Social as quoted from the DataIndonesia.id page, there were 556 million Twitter users worldwide in January 2023. Indonesia accounted for 24 million of these Twitter users. It is no surprise that Twitter is one of the most popular social media platforms. Numerous features allow users to share stories through writing, sharing information, and even exchanging messages. Twitter is the most up-to-date social media platform, so information spreads quickly. As a result, many bilingual and multilingual users code-switch when discussing a topic, asserting something, or inadvertently doing so, as explained by Hoffman (1991) in his discussion of the reasons for code-switching. The widespread use of bilingual code-switching between Indonesian and English on Twitter piques the writer's interest in borrowing the topic of code-switching from one of the Twitter accounts. This study analyzed code-switching based on its type and the reason for its use, as taken from one of the Twitter accounts, @natanattda, which frequently used language changes in her tweets. This study examined the contextual and grammatical types of code-switching on Twitter and explained why the audience did it. However, this study will only discuss tweets from the @natanattda account that contain code-switching from 2021 to 2022 only.

2. Method

The method of this was divided into three parts: the data source, the methods and techniques of data collection, and the method of data analysis. The analysis in this study used a qualitative approach. The three parts of this study's research method will be discussed further below.

The primary data of this study was from one of the Twitter social media accounts user @natanattda. Twitter is a medium that allows users to send tweets in the form of text, photos, and videos. It was chosen because social media Twitter is widely used in Indonesia. Because of its broad reach, information spreads quickly in the Twitter application. This is also supported by the trending feature, which informs users about recent discussion topics. There are several accounts that have many followers who often tweet using two languages, Indonesian and English. One Twitter user who has many followers is user @natanattda. User @natanattda joined Twitter in 2012 and has 49.5k followers. This user claims that the Twitter account with user @natanattda is for fun, such as discussing the user's favorite artist.

The documentation method was used to collect the data through library research, which means that the data were taken from the social media Twitter was obtained by searching the Twitter website on the internet. There were five steps in the technique of collecting the data. First, the researchers searched the Twitter website on the internet by using devices such as a laptop. Second, the researchers typed into the Twitter account search bar, @natanattda, and limited the search for tweets only from 2021 to 2022. Third, look carefully at tweets from the @natanattda account that contain code-switching. Last, classify what type of code-switching that was contained in a tweet from user @natanattda, and start analyzing the data according to the types and reasons based on the theory.

The descriptive qualitative method was used in conducting this study. This method is a method that focuses on in-depth observations and will give more explanation about the data. The qualitative method was used because there is no numerical or statistical data in this study, and the data will be described descriptively. After collecting all required data, the utterances

containing illocutionary acts were analyzed. The technique of analyzing the data was done by defining the analysis descriptively. The first step was to analyze the types of code-switching by applying the theory written by Poplack in Romaine (1995, p.122-123). According to Poplack (1995), there are three types of code-switching. There are tag-switching, inter-sentential switching, and intra-sentential switching. The last was to analyze the reasons for code-switching by applying the theory written by Hoffman (1991). According to Hoffman (1991, p.115), there are seven reasons for code-switching. There are talking about a particular topic, quoting somebody else, being emphatic about something (expressing solidarity), interjection (inserting sentence fillers or sentence connectors), repetition used for clarification, the intention of clarifying the speech, content for the interlocutor, and expressing group identity.

3. Discussion

3.1. Finding

Table 4.1 The Frequency and the Occurrence Percentage of Types of Code Switching found in Twitter account @natanattda (2021-2022)

No	Types of Code-switching	Frequency	Percentage of Occurrence (%)
1.	Tag-switching	1	14.3%
2.	Inter-sentential Switching	4	57.1%
3.	Intra-sentential Switching	2	28.6%
TOTAL		7	100%

Table 4.1 shows the types of code-switching from the data sources obtained. There are a total of 7 data found from data sources. The most dominant data found was Inter-sentential Switching with 4 data or 57.1%, followed by Intra-sentential Switching with 2 data or 28.6%, and Tag-switching with 1 data or 14.3%. Inter-sentential switching is the most common type of tweet by user @natanattda. This factor can be caused by the ability of @natanattda users who are fluent in two languages, both Indonesian and English.

3.2. Discussion

In analyzing the data, there are two theories by experts used. The first is the theory regarding the types of code-switching proposed by Poplack in Romaine (1995). The second is regarding the reasons why code-switching is used, proposed by Hoffman (1991). A more detailed explanation will be explained further below.

Tag-switching

Tag-switching is the insertion of a tag in one language into another language in utterance. There is only one data of tag-switching found in the Twitter account @natanattda.

Data 1

“Well.... *enggga salah*” (User @natanattda / 22-10-21)

(Well.... it’s not wrong)

The context of the tweet from @natanattda was about an artist’s picture posing and biting a necklace. Then user @natanattda uploaded the picture with the caption *do you know what else can be bitten?* After that, one of the mutual friends answered with one of the brands for ulcer medicine. Then, user @natanattda replied *Well.... enggga salah*.

The type of code-switching from the sentence above is Tag-switching because the user inserted a tag word *well* at the beginning of the sentence before using Indonesian. The function of code-switching from the sentence above is talking about a particular topic because the user tried to express her opinion about a particular topic that was discussed. She stated her opinion by saying that it was not totally wrong.

Inter-sentential Switching

Inter-sentential switching involves a large amount of syntactic complexity and conformance to the rules of both languages; therefore, speakers who make this kind of transition are usually quite proficient in the participating languages because most utterances must conform to the rules of both languages. There are three inter-sentential switchings found in the Twitter account @natanattda.

Data 1

I don't know *sih sebenarnya kalau misalnya aku sama pasanganku bakal kayak gimana... lupa kapan terakhir jatuh cinta...* (User @natanattda / 30-12-21)

(I don't know what it would be like if I and my partner... forget when I last fell in love)

The context in the tweet from @natanattda was about her conversation with her friend through the messaging application. Then user @natanattda added that she does not know what will happen if she exchanges messages with her partner because it has been a long time.

The type of code-switching from the sentence above is inter-sentential switching because the user involves a large amount of syntactic complexity in the form of sentences and also adapts to the rules of both languages (English and Indonesian). The sentence was started with an English sentence, then followed by Indonesian. The function of code-switching from the sentence above is talking about a particular topic because the user gives her opinion about a particular topic that is discussed. She stated her opinion by saying that she is not sure what it would be like for her and her partner since she forgets when the last time she fell in love which means, it happened a long time ago.

Data 2

It’s still fascinating to me the fact that svt members are soooooo in sync *tapi kalau kalian focus ke masing masing orang cara gerak mereka beda beda*” (User @natanattda / 16-04-22)

(It’s still fascinating to me the fact that svt members are soooooo in sync but if you focus on each member, the way the move is different)

The context of the tweet from @natanattda was about a video featuring Korean idol groups dancing in sync. User @natanattda commented on the video in admiration that with so many people, they are still very synchronized in dancing even though each of them has different dancing characteristics.

The type of code-switching from the sentence above is inter-sentential switching because the user involves a large amount of syntactic complexity in the form of sentences and also adapts to the rules of both languages (English and Indonesian). The sentence was started with an English sentence, then followed by Indonesian. The function of code-switching from the sentence above is talking about a particular topic because the user tried to express her opinion about a particular topic that was discussed. She stated her opinion by saying that someone famous is so synchronized but also has a different style of dancing.

Data 3

“Dulu hao pernah pake temporary tattoo and I thought it was legit real bcs he looks good with it” (Insert a picture about Hao (the one she mentioned before) wear a temporary tattoo) (User @natanattda / 04-05-21)

(Hao used to wear a temporary tattoo a tattoo and I thought it was legit real because he looks good with it)

The context of the tweet from @natanattda discussed her favorite Korean idol group if they use real tattoos. User @natanattda commented on this by adding that one of the idol group members would look good if he has real tattoos.

The type of code-switching from the sentence above is inter-sentential switching because the user involves a large amount of syntactic complexity in the form of sentences and also adapts to the rules of both languages (English and Indonesian). The sentence was started with an Indonesian sentence, then followed by English. The function of code-switching from the sentence above is talking about a particular topic because the user tried to express her opinion about a particular topic that was discussed. She stated her opinion by saying that the artist (Hao) is cool if he has a real tattoo. This is because the artist has previously used a temporary tattoo, and it looks really cool, according to user @natanattda.

Data 4

“Dulu bapak baru pulang setahun sekali pas lebaran aja. Paling gak suka ketika libur panjang selesai. Aku pasti nangis ketika beliau mulai angkat koper lagi. That's why i cherish every eid moment we have together ♥” (User @natanattda / 01-05-22)

(Dad used to back home once a year when holiday only. I really hate when the holiday is over. I will definitely be crying when he lifts his suitcase. That's why I cherish every Eid moment we have together)

The context in the tweet from @natanattda discussed the Eid memories back then. User @natanattda recalled that she would be very sad when the Eid holidays were over because she had to part with his father. Users claimed that in the past, her father could only come home during Eid al-Fitr. Therefore, she really values togetherness with family during the holidays.

The type of code-switching from the sentence above is inter-sentential switching because the user involves a large amount of syntactic complexity in the form of sentences and also adapts to the rules of both languages (English and Indonesian). The sentence started with an Indonesian sentence, then followed by English. The function of code-switching from the sentence above is being emphatic about something (Express Solidarity) because the user was not using her first language to emphasize something. After all, it is easier to empathize and express the emotion she felt about spending time with her dad when holiday in English.

Intra-sentential Switching

Intra-sentential switching refers to the transition that occurs in the same clause or sentence in the middle of a sentence containing elements of both languages. There are two data of intra-sentential switching found in the Twitter account @natanattda.

Data 1

*“Kalau akusih **garden wedding** minimalis mas, tapi kalau kamu maunya sewa **ballroom** it’s okay aku ngikut aja hehe”* (User @natanattda / 26-05-21)

(If I can choose, I’ll choose a minimalist garden wedding babe, but if you want to rent a ballroom it’s okay, I’ll go with you)

The context of the tweet from @natanattda was about a singer video. User @natanattda uploaded the video with the caption, *kalau akusih garden wedding minimalis mas, tapi kalau kamu maunya sewa ballroom it’s okay aku ngikut aja hehe*. The meaning of the user’s tweet is that she is so fascinated with the artist that she imagines how to celebrate their wedding in the future.

The type of code-switching from the sentence above is intra-sentential switching. The user did the transition that occurs in the same clause or sentence in the middle of a sentence containing elements of both languages (English and Indonesian). The sentence started with Indonesian-English-Indonesian, and back to English again. The function of code-switching from the sentence above is talking about a particular topic because the user tried to express her opinion about a particular topic that was discussed. She stated her opinion by saying that it was okay if the man she talked about chose to rent a ballroom for their wedding arrangement.

Data 2

*“Woahhh... **sorry** ya kak di **thread** rekomendasinya tadi banyak **zombienya**....”* (User @natanattda / 06-05-22)

(Ow... I’m sorry that the recommendation thread is full of zombies)

The context of the tweet from @natanattda was about a video from the zombie series. User @natanattda uploaded series footage in the form of a video on her Twitter to compare the series about zombies that she had watched. Then one of the mutual friends replied that she would love to watch the series if only she did not have a phobia of zombies. Then with regret, the user @natanattda apologized for uploading the video, which can trigger the phobia.

The type of code-switching from the sentence above is intra-sentential switching. The user did the transition that occurs in the same clause or sentence in the middle of a sentence containing elements of both languages (English and Indonesian). The sentence started with Indonesian-English-Indonesian, and back to English again but with an Indonesian affix (-nya). The function of code-switching from the sentence above is being emphatic about something (Express Solidarity) because the user did not use her first language to emphasize something. It is easier to empathize and express her apologies to her friend in a second language than in a first language.

After analyzing the data above, it can be concluded that the most dominant type of code-switching is Inter-sentential switching. From the seven reasons for using the code-switching theory proposed by Hoffman (1991), only two reasons found from this account's tweets include talking about a particular topic and being emphatic about something (expressing solidarity). The most dominant reason for using code-switching found in the data is talking about a

particular topic. According to her tweet, the user @natanattda frequently uses the same two languages when uploading or communicating with others. As a result, it can be concluded that she is fluent in two languages.

4. Conclusion

As stated in the study objectives, there are several points based on the findings of this study. There is research on types and reasons for code-switching in the @natanattda Twitter account. First, consider the type of code-switching contained in @natanattda's tweet, which is restricted to the years 2021-2022. Second, the reasons for using code-switching are contained in @natanattda's tweet. From the analysis results above, it can be concluded that the owner of the Twitter account @natanattda often uses code-switching between Indonesian as her first language and English as her second language.

By using the theory of types of code-switching written by Poplack in Romaine (1995), the data that contained code-switching found in her tweets had all three types. Namely tag-switching, inter-sentential switching, and intra-sentential switching. The most dominant data found was Inter-sentential Switching with 4 data or 57.1%, followed by Intra-sentential Switching with 2 data or 28.6%, and Tag-switching with 1 data or 14.3% Inter-sentential switching is the most common type of tweet by user @natanattda. The factor that the owner of @natanattda uses the Inter-sentential switching type more often can be caused by the ability of the user who is fluent in two languages, namely Indonesian and English. Using the theory of reasons for using code-switching written by Hoffman (1991), only two pieces of data were found in the tweets of the Twitter account @natanattda. Namely, talking about a particular topic and being empathic about something (expressing solidarity). Talking about a particular topic is the reason that is most used in data. The factor that can trigger this can be concluded because the user @natanattda is able to master two languages well (bilingual). This can be seen from the frequent use of code-switching using Indonesian and English at every opportunity and with various topics discussed. Not only that, but this also indicates that most Indonesians are able to master two or more languages by communicating using Indonesian and English on Twitter.

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